

**DAVLAT TILINI RIVOJLANTIRISH YO‘LIDA QABUL QILINGAN
QONUNLAR TAHLILI
ANALYSIS OF THE LAWS ADOPTED FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE
STATE LANGUAGE**

*Shahrisabz State Pedagogical Institute Pre-school education students of group 3-21
(external)*

***Saidova Margiyona
Hamroyeva Nigina***

Annotatsiya : Ushbu maqolada O‘zbekiston Respublikasining davlat tili hisoblangan o‘zbek tili haqida umumiy ma’lumot berilgan hamda davlat tilini rivojlantirish yo‘lidagi qabul qilingan qonunlar o‘rganilib, ularning tahliliga alohida urg‘u qaratilgan. Ayniqsa bugungi kunda o‘zbek tilida ish yuritish va o‘zbek tilini rivojlantirish masalalari ko‘zda tutilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Qonun, o‘zbektili, davlat tili, tahlil, mamlakatimiz. rivojlantirish, yangi so‘zlar.

Abstract: This article provides general information about the Uzbek language, which is the state language of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and examines the adopted laws for the development of the state language, with special emphasis on their analysis. Especially today, issues of doing business in Uzbek and developing the Uzbek language are considered.

Key words: Law, Uzbek, state language, analysis, our country. development, new words.

KIRISH

Davlat tili muayyan davlatning qonun chiqaruvchi, ijro etuvchi va sud hokimiyati organlarining rasmiy tilidir. Odatda, ko'p millatli mamlakatlarda: Hindiston, Kanada, Shveytsariya, qaysi til yoki tillar rasmiy ekanligi ularning konstitutsiyalarida belgilanadi. Aksariyat mamlakatlarda rasmiy til va davlat tili aynan bir xil. Faqat ayrim mamlakatlarda rasmiy til davlat tili maqomidan farq qiladi. Masalan, Shveytsariyada konstitutsiyaga ko‘ra, nemis, fransuz va italyan tillari rasmiy til hisoblanadi; Nemis, fransuz, italyan, romansh tillari davlat tillaridir.[1]

INTRODUCTION

State language is the official language of a specific country for law-making, executive and judicial authorities. Usually, in multinational countries: India, Canada, Switzerland, which language or languages are official is defined in their constitutions. In most countries, the official language and the state language are exactly the same. Only in some countries does the official language differ from the status of the state language. For example, in Switzerland, according to the constitution, German, French, and Italian are the official languages; German, French, Italian and Romansh languages are the state languages.[1]

MATERIALLAR VA METODLAR

O‘zbekistonda sovetlar hukmronligi davrida davlat tili haqida umuman gapirish mumkin emas edi, aksincha, o‘zbek tilining ijtimoiy hayotda qo‘llanilishi tobora cheklanib bordi. Jamiyatni qayta qurish ma’naviy poklanishni boshlab berdi. Natijada «O‘zbekiston Respublikasining Davlat tili to‘g‘risida»gi qonun qabul qilindi (1989 yil 21 oktyabr). Bu qonun o‘zbek xalqining milliy ongini yuksaltirishda, mamlakat mustaqilligini mustahkamlashda, madaniy merosni tiklashda muhim rol o‘ynadi. Ushbu qonun qoidalari O‘zbekiston Konstitutsiyasida mustahkamlab qo‘yildi. Konstitutsiyaning 4-moddasiga ko‘ra, O‘zbekistonning davlat tili o‘zbek tilidir. Qoraqalpog‘istonda bu maqom qoraqalpoq tiliga ham berilgan. Mamlakatimizda ro‘y berayotgan real jarayon va imkoniyatlarni hisobga olgan holda lotin yozuviga asoslangan o‘zbek alifbosini bosqichma-bosqich joriy etish vazifasi til islohoti bilan bog‘liq masalalarga zarur tuzatishlar kiritish zaruriyatini yuzaga keltirdi. mustahkamlash sharoitida qabul qilingan davlat tili haqidagi qonunning ko‘plab moddalariga o‘zgartish va qo‘shimchalar kiritishni talab qildi. Natijada 1995-yil 22-dekabrda O‘zbekiston Respublikasining “Davlat tili to‘g‘risida”gi qonunining yangi tahriri qabul qilindi[2]. O‘zbek tilining O‘zbekiston Respublikasi hududida davlat tili sifatidagi huquqiy asoslari ushbu qonun va boshqalar bilan belgilangan. qonunlar bilan belgilanadi. O‘zbekiston Respublikasida barcha fuqarolarning davlat tilini o‘rganishi uchun shart-sharoit yaratilib, millat va elatlarning tillariga hurmat bilan munosabatda bo‘lib, ularning rivojlanishi ta’minlanmoqda.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

During the rule of the Soviets in Uzbekistan, it was not possible to talk about the state language at all, on the contrary, the use of the Uzbek language in social life was increasingly limited. The reconstruction of society started a spiritual purification. As a result, the law "On the State Language of the Republic of Uzbekistan" was adopted

(October 21, 1989). This law played an important role in the development of the national consciousness of the Uzbek people, in the strengthening of the country's independence, and in the restoration of the cultural heritage. The provisions of this law were enshrined in the Constitution of Uzbekistan. According to Article 4 of the Constitution, the state language of Uzbekistan is Uzbek. In Karakalpakstan, this status is also given to the Karakalpak language. Taking into account the real processes and opportunities taking place in the country, the task of gradually implementing the Uzbek alphabet based on the Latin script in stages created the need to make necessary amendments to the issues related to language reform. required amendments and additions to many articles of the law on the state language, which was adopted in a context of strengthening. As a result, on December 22, 1995, the new version of the Law on the State Language of the Republic of Uzbekistan was adopted[2]. The legal basis of the Uzbek language as a state language in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan is provided by this law and others. determined by laws. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, conditions are created for all citizens to learn the state language, and the languages of nations and peoples are treated with respect and their development is ensured.

TADQIQOT VA MUHOKAZA

“2020-2030-yillarda o‘zbek tilini rivojlantirish va til siyosatini takomillashtirish” konsepsiyasining mazmun-mohiyati to‘g‘risida

O‘zbek tilining xalqimiz ijtimoiy hayotida va xalqaro miqyosdagi nufuzini tubdan oshirish, o‘zib borayotgan yoshlarimizni vatanparvarlik, milliy an‘ana va qadriyatlarimizga sadoqat ruhida tarbiyalash, buyuk ajdodlarimizning boy merosini meros qilib olish. , mamlakatimizda davlat tili bo‘lishini ta‘minlashda tilga oid qabul qilingan qonunlar, farmonlar va boshqa huquqiy hujjatlar ijrosini izchil ta‘minlashda muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Shu munosabat bilan O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Shavkat Mirziyoevning 21-oktabrdagi “O‘zbek tilining davlat tili sifatidagi nufuzi va mavqeyini tubdan oshirish chora-tadbirlari to‘g‘risida”gi farmoni qabul qilindi. O‘zbek tiliga davlat tili maqomi berilganiga 30 yil to‘ldi. yubiley munosabati bilan imzolandi va 21 oktabr “O‘zbek tili bayrami” deb e‘lon qilindi.

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2019-yil 21-oktabrdagi PF-5850-son qaroriga asosan Vazirlar Mahkamasi huzuridagi Davlat tilini rivojlantirish departamenti tashkil etildi. 2020-yil 20-oktabrda O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining “Mamlakatimizda o‘zbek tilini yanada rivojlantirish va til siyosatini takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari to‘g‘risida”gi farmoni qabul qilingan bo‘lib,

mazkur Farmon asosida “O‘zbek tili va tilini rivojlantirish siyosatni takomillashtirish konsepsiyasi” ishlab chiqildi. Kontsepsiyaning asosiy yo‘nalishlari quyidagilardan iborat:

2025 yilgacha davlat maktabgacha ta‘lim tizimida o‘zbek tilida so‘zlashuvchi guruhlarni qamrab olishni 72 foizga, 2030 yilgacha esa 80 foizga yetkazish;

2030-yilgacha umumta‘lim maktablarida o‘quv yillari uchun bazaviy o‘quv dasturlarida ona tili fanini o‘qitish hajmini amaldagi 84 soatdan haftasiga 110 soatgacha oshirish; oliy ta‘lim muassasalarida o‘zbek tili kafedralari sonini 2025 yilgacha 120 taga, 2030 yilgacha esa 140 taga yetkazish; “O‘zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi”ning jildlarini lotin yozuviga asoslangan o‘zbek alifbosida nashr etishni bosqichma-bosqich oshirish; 2020-yilda o‘zbek tilining lug‘at boyligini oshiradigan 15 ta lingvistik, soha-terminologik, izohli lug‘atlarni yaratish; 2030-yilgacha tele va radioboshlovchilarni o‘zbek adabiy tili bo‘yicha qayta tayyorlash kurslarida tayyorlash tizimini joriy etish va qamrab olishni 100 foizga yetkazish; 2025-yilga qadar tarmoq boshqaruv hujjatlarining davlat tilida yagona elektron namunalarini ishlab chiqish va ulardan foydalanish bo‘yicha 14 ta onlayn-dasturlarni ishlab chiqish va bu ko‘rsatkichni 2030-yilga borib 25 taga yetkazish; dasturiy mahsulotlar va elektron lug‘at dasturlarining o‘zbekcha ilovalarini yaratish; chet elliklar uchun o‘zbek tilini o‘rgatish dasturlarini yaratish; 2030 yilgacha xorijiy oliy ta‘lim muassasalarida o‘zbek tilini o‘rgatuvchi markazlar sonini hozirgi 17 tadan 60 taga yetkazish; “O‘zbek tili do‘stlari” to‘garaklari sonini 2025 yilgacha 30 taga, 2030 yilgacha esa 40 taga yetkazish[3].

Bugun ona tilimiz tom ma‘noda davlat tiliga aylanib, xalqimizni yurtimizda erkin va farovon hayot barpo etishdek ulug‘ maqsadlar sari safarbar etuvchi beqiyos kuch sifatida maydonga chiqdi, desak mubolag‘a bo‘lmaydi. Har birimiz davlat tiliga e‘tiborni mustaqillikka e‘tibor, davlat tiliga hurmat va sadoqat, ona Vatanga hurmat va sadoqat deb bilishimiz, bu qarashni hayotimiz qoidasiga aylantirishimiz kerak. Bu ezgu harakatni barchamiz o‘zimizdan, oilamizdan, mahallamizdan boshlashimiz, ona tilimiz, an‘ana va qadriyatlarimizni e‘zozlash, Vatanga muhabbatimizni amaliy faoliyatda namoyon etishimiz zarur. Shu bois Konsepsiyaga ko‘ra, “O‘zbek tilining izohli lug‘ati” ko‘p jildligining yangi nashri (kirill va lotin yozuvlari asosidagi o‘zbek alifbosida); “O‘zbek tilining imlo lug‘ati”, “O‘zbek tili sinonimlari lug‘ati”, “O‘zbek tili sinonimlarining katta izohli lug‘ati”, “O‘zbek tili frazeologiyasining katta izohli lug‘ati”. “O‘zbek tili omonimlari lug‘ati”ni yaratish vazifasi qo‘yildi.

Biroq shu o‘rinda shuni aytish kerakki, ayrim joylarda til masalasida qalbni zerikarli qiladigan holatlar ham uchrab turadi. Xususan, ko‘chalardagi do‘konlar, supermarketlar, turli ustaxonalar shoxobchalari, go‘zallik salonlari, turli osmono‘par binolar, bog‘chalar nomlari o‘zbek tilida emas, balki boshqa xorijiy tillarda yozilganiga guvoh bo‘lamiz[4]. Bu haqiqatni isbotlash uchun katta ilmiy izlanishlar qilish shart emas, qo‘lingizga ruchka, qalam olib ko‘chaga chiqish kifoya. Qanchalik achinarli bo‘lsa-da, biz bunga ko‘nikib ketyapmiz! Axir biz O‘zbekistonda yashaymiz, nega joylarni o‘zbekcha nomlay olmaymiz? Bunga kim aybdor: davlat hokimiyati yoki o‘zbek millati? Ijtimoiy tarmoqlarda O‘zbekistonda osmono‘par binolar qurilayotganiga qaramay, ularning nomlari hamon ingliz tilida ekani haqida turli fikrlarga duch kelishimiz mumkin.

Zero, til har bir xalqning ko‘zgusi, uning ma’naviy ko‘zgidir. Til bor ekan, millat barhayotdir. Tilni onaga qiyoslash bejiz aytilmagan, inson onasini ko‘rmasdan, uning sof mehrini, mehrini his qilmasdan yashay olmaydi. Bu fikrimizga dalil sifatida O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Shavkat Mirziyoyevning o‘zbek tiliga davlat tili maqomi berilganining 30 yilligiga bag‘ishlangan tantanali marosimdagi ma’ruzasini keltirishimiz mumkin: agar his etmoqchi bo‘lsa. imkoniyatlaridan kelib chiqib, munis onalarimiz xudolari, ming yillik dostonlarimiz, o‘lmas maqomlarimizni tinglashi, baxshi va hofizlarimizning sehrlil qo‘shiqlarini tinglashi kerak[5].

RESEARCH AND DISCUSSION

Regarding the essence of the concept of "development of the Uzbek language and improvement of the language policy in 2020-2030"

To fundamentally increase the prestige of the Uzbek language in the social life of our people and at the international level, to educate our growing youth in the spirit of patriotism, loyalty to national traditions and values, and to inherit the rich heritage of our great ancestors, to make the state language in our country The adopted laws, decrees and other legal documents related to the language play an important role in ensuring smooth implementation. In this regard, the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoev dated October 21 "On measures to fundamentally increase the prestige and position of the Uzbek language as a state language" was adopted. It is 30 years since the status of the state language was granted to the Uzbek language. was signed on the occasion of the anniversary, and October 21 was declared "Uzbek language holiday".

According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5850 of October 21, 2019, the Department of State Language Development of the Cabinet

of Ministers was established. On October 20, 2020, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further develop the Uzbek language and improve language policy in our country" was adopted, and based on this Decree, "Development of the Uzbek language and language the concept of policy improvement" was developed. The main directions of the concept include the following:

To increase the coverage of Uzbek-speaking groups to 72% in the state preschool education system by 2025, and to 80% by 2030;

By 2030, increase the scope of teaching the subject of the mother tongue in the basic curricula for the academic years in general education schools from the current 84 hours to 110 hours per week; increase the number of Uzbek language departments in higher education institutions to 120 by 2025, and to 140 by 2030; to gradually increase the publication of the volumes of the "Uzbekistan national encyclopedia" in the Uzbek alphabet based on the Latin script; In 2020, creating 15 linguistic, field-terminological, explanatory dictionaries that increase the vocabulary of the Uzbek language; to introduce a training system in the retraining courses of TV and radio presenters in Uzbek literary language and increase the coverage to 100% by 2030; By 2025, to develop 14 online programs for the development and use of uniform electronic samples of sectoral administrative documents in the state language, and to increase this indicator to 25 by 2030; creation of Uzbek applications of software products and electronic dictionary programs; creating Uzbek language teaching programs for foreigners; Increase the number of Uzbek language teaching centers in foreign higher education institutions from the current 17 to 60 by 2030; To increase the number of "Friends of the Uzbek language" clubs to 30 by 2025, and to 40 by 2030[3].

It is not an exaggeration to say that today our mother tongue has literally become the state language and has emerged as an incomparable force that mobilizes our people to great goals such as building a free and prosperous life in our country. Each of us should regard attention to the state language as attention to independence, respect and loyalty to the state language, respect and loyalty to the motherland, and make this view the rule of our lives. We should all start this noble movement from ourselves, our family and community, respect our mother tongue, traditions and values, and show our love for the Motherland in practical activities. Therefore, according to the Concept, a new edition of the multi-volume "Annotated Dictionary of the Uzbek Language" (in the Uzbek alphabet based on the Cyrillic and Latin scripts); "Spelling

dictionary of the Uzbek language", "Dictionary of Uzbek language synonyms", "Large explanatory dictionary of synonyms of the Uzbek language", "Large explanatory dictionary of phraseology of the Uzbek language". The task of creating the "Dictionary of Uzbek language homonyms" was assigned.

However, it should be noted here that in some places there are also cases that make the heart dull in the matter of language. In particular, we can witness that the names of shops, supermarkets, various workshop branches, beauty salons, various skyscrapers, and kindergartens on the streets are not written in Uzbek, but in other foreign languages[4] . To prove this fact, you don't need to do a huge scientific research, it's enough to go out into the street with a pen and a pen in your hand. Despite how sad it is, we are getting used to it! After all, we live in Uzbekistan, why can't we name places in Uzbek? Who is to blame for this: state authorities or the Uzbek nation? In social networks, despite the fact that skyscrapers are being built in Uzbekistan, we may come across different opinions that their names are still in English.

After all, language is the mirror of every nation, its spiritual reflection. As long as there is a language, the nation is alive. It is not for nothing that the language is compared to the mother, a person cannot live without seeing his mother, without feeling her pure love and affection. As a proof of this opinion, we can cite the speech delivered by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev on the occasion of the 30th anniversary of the granting of the status of the state language to the Uzbek language: if he wants to feel his possibilities, he should listen to the gods of our munis mothers, our thousand-year epics, our immortal statuses, and listen to the magical songs of our bakhshi and hafiz[5]."

XULOSA

Umuman olganda, "2020-2030-yillarda o'zbek tilini rivojlantirish va til siyosatini takomillashtirish konsepsiyasi"ni amalga oshirishdan ko'zlangan maqsad mamlakatimiz hayotining barcha jabhalarida, jumladan, davlat boshqaruvi, zamonaviy va innovatsion texnologiyalar, sanoat, bank-moliya tizimi, huquqshunoslik, diplomatiya, harbiy ish. , tibbiyot va boshqa sohalarida davlat tili imkoniyatlaridan to'liq va to'g'ri foydalanishga erishish, barcha davlat organlari va tashkilotlarida davlat tilida ishlash salohiyatiga ega malakali kadrlar faoliyat yuritishini ta'minlash. Shu bilan birga, ilmiy asoslangan yangi so'z va atamalar muntazam ravishda rasmiy muomalaga kiritilmoqda, fanning barcha sohalariga oid ilmiy tadqiqotlarda davlat tili fan tili sifatida nufuzga ega bo'lib, o'zbek tilining o'quv

leksikografiyasi tarmog'ini rivojlantirishga qaratilgan. zamonaviy, yangi avlod o'quv lug'atlari va ularning elektron shakllarini yaratish orqali milliy terminologiya tizimini sohalar bo'yicha takomillashtirish. O'zbek tili va adabiyoti o'qitishning yangi, zamonaviy metodikasini yaratish orqali esa til ta'limi samaradorligini oshirish mumkin.

CONCLUSION

In general, the goal of the implementation of the "concept of the development of the Uzbek language and improvement of the language policy in 2020-2030" is in all spheres of the country's life, including public administration, modern and innovative technologies, industry, the banking and financial system, jurisprudence, diplomacy, military work. , to achieve full and correct use of the capabilities of the state language in medicine and other fields, to ensure that qualified personnel with the potential to work in the state language work in all state bodies and organizations. At the same time, new scientifically based words and terms are regularly introduced into official circulation, the state language has authority as the language of science in scientific researches related to all branches of science, development of the Uzbek language educational lexicography network, it is aimed to improve the national terminological system by fields by creating modern, new generation educational dictionaries and their electronic forms. And by creating a new, modern methodology of teaching the Uzbek language and literature, it is possible to increase the effectiveness of language education.

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